

Parkinson's Disease Identification using KNN and ANN Algorithm based on Voice Disorder

DISSERTATION

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the MTech Data Science and Engineering

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By

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Dissertation entitled “Parkinson’s Disease Identification using KNN and ANN Algorithm based on Voice Disorder” and submitted by Mr. Shinde Harshit Vasant Nutan ID No. 2020FA04047 in partial fulfilment of the requirements of DSECLZG628T Dissertation, embodies the work done by him/her under my supervision.

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DSECLZG628T DISSERTATION

Dissertation Title : Parkinson's Disease Identification using KNN & ANN Algorithm based on Voice Recorder

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ABSTRACT

Speech signal processing has gotten a lot of attention recently because of how widely used it is. In this project work, we conducted a comparative analysis for effective dysphonia (a voice disorder) and Parkinson's disease detection using machine learning classifiers. In order to distinguish between PD patients and healthy individuals, we used Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and K Nearest Neighbours (KNN) algorithms to demonstrate a robust detection process. According to experimental findings, the ANN classifier outperformed the KNN classifier on average in terms of accuracy. The UCI Experiment consists of 31 subjects of which 23 were diagnosed with Parkinson's disease. Using ANN, the established system has a 96.7% accuracy rate for separating healthy individuals from a range of PD patients.

Keywords:

Parkinson, disease, detection, accuracy, diagnosis, methods, pd, classifier, evaluation, symptoms, matrix, ANN, KNN, dysphonia

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ABBREVIATIONS

A

Artificial Neural Networks
ANN, 4, 18

B

Batch Back Propagation
BBP, 42

C

classifier, classification and regression trees
CART, 19
Computerized Speech Laboratory
CSL, 39
Computerized Tomography
CT, 10, 13, 34
convolutional neural networks and bidirectional long short term
CNN-BLSTM, 17, 18

D

decision tree
DT, 19, 21
deep learning
DL, 17, 19

F

Fast Fourier Transform
FFT, 20

G

Gradient Descent
GD, 42

H

Harmonic To Noise ratio
HNR, 10, 40

I

Industrial Acoustics Company
IAC, 39

K

K Nearest Neighbours
KNN, 4

L

Levenberg-Marquardt
LM, 42
Levodopa
L-DOPA, 24
logistic regression
LR, 16, 20, 21
long-short-term memory
LSTM, 15

M

Matthews' correlation coefficient
MCC, 11
Monoamine oxidase B
MAO-B, 24

P

Parkinson Disease
PD, 4, 6, 7, 10, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28,
29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 44
principal component analysis - artificial neural network
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R

random forest
RF, 17, 19

S

single-photon emission computerized tomography
SPECT, 10, 13
Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
SMOTE, 17, 19

U

UC Irvine
UCI, 4, 16, 18, 19, 20
Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
UPDRS, 16

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The effects of neurodegenerative disease on people are felt on a social, economic, and professional level. It is a pathology that gradually destroys nerve cells by affecting the brain and nervous system. Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases are the most well-known and prevalent ones. Particularly connected to the loss of dopamine-producing neurons in the basic ganglia is Parkinson's disease. In actuality, Parkinson's disease medication costs are very high. There is currently no known cure. Medication is only used for early-stage treatments that aim to enhance the patient's quality of life.

There are several ways to identify Parkinson's disease symptoms, but most of them call for motor actions that don't show up until the disease has progressed significantly.

The most common traditional methods for diagnosing the disease are pricy invasive methods like SPECT and CT tomography, which are primarily effective in the advanced stages of the illness. Apart from conventional approaches, practitioners take a variety of diagnostic routes. Some of them were based on handwriting by taking into account the connection between nervous system issues and handwriting. Others have used peripheral biomarkers to identify PD early.

The current study focuses on diagnostic pathways based on voice analysis. In fact, the focus of current PD telemedicine studies is voice-based systems. Thus, the information required for the assessment of PD has been extracted using a variety of speech signal processing algorithms. To create trustworthy decision support systems, the extracted characteristics are fed into learning algorithms.

Fundamental frequency, jitter, shimmer, and HNR are currently the acoustic parameters most frequently used in acoustic analysis applications and most frequently cited in the literature.

The number of times the vocal cords repeat a produced sound wave over the course of a given period is known as the fundamental frequency (F_0), expressed in hertz. The number of times the glottis opens and closes is another factor. For various genders and ages, this frequency falls within a typical range of values. But because F_0 is also used to transmit prosody, these values are not constant.

The parameter of frequency variation from one cycle to the next is known as jitter. It is primarily impacted by the vocal cords' inability to vibrate in a controlled manner; patients with pathologies frequently have voices with higher levels of jitter. According to the majority of researchers, the sustained phonation rate for adults is between 0.5% and 1.0%.

The term "shimmer" describes changes in the amplitude of the sound wave. It alters in response to diminished glottal resistance, severe vocal cord damage, and the presence of sound and breathing. For

values between 0.4 and 1% for children and below 3% for adults, it is regarded as pathological voice.

The use of various classifiers is the foundation for Parkinson's disease detection. Measurement criteria, such as classification accuracy, Matthews' correlation coefficient (MCC), Spearman correlation coefficient, specificity, sensitivity, F-score (F- measure), etc., are used to distinguish between them. Each of these measurement criteria has formulas to calculate it and conclude which is the most qualitatively adequate classifier for the study.

We must pay close attention to the confusion matrix before defining these criteria. A contingency table is a tool for evaluating how well a learning model performs in classification problems by determining how closely its predictions match the truth.

		Predicted Class	
		<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
Actual Class	<i>Positive</i>	(TP)	(FN)
	<i>Negative</i>	(FP)	(TN)

Table 1: Shows the confusion matrix for a two-class classifier

TP (True Positive): the prediction is positive while the actual real value is positive.

TN (True Negative): the prediction is negative while the actual real value is negative.

FP (False Positive): the prediction is positive while the actual real value is negative.

FN (False Negative): the prediction is negative while the actual real value is positive.

a) Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC):

$$MCC = \frac{TP.TN - FP.FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP).(TP + FN).(TN + FP).(TN + FN)}} \quad (1)$$

The binary and multi-class classification quality is measured using this coefficient. The true, false, positive, and negative are the foundation of it. It gives back a value between -1 and 1.

(1): Perfect classifier (perfect prediction).

(0): No better than random prediction.

(-1): Contradiction between prediction and observation.

b) Spearman correlation coefficient:

This coefficient examines nonlinear monotonic relationships (if one of the variables increases, the other does the same, and vice versa).

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (2)$$

n: number of observations.

$d_i = g(X_i) - rg(Y_i)$: The difference between the two rows of each observation

c) Classification accuracy, specificity, sensitivity:

On the basis of the confusion matrix, the classification model can be assessed. The performance measures are then derived from the evaluation results.

Precision: Represents the proportion of correct predictions among the points that have been predicted positives.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

Accuracy: the number of correct predictions made by the model over all kinds predictions made.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4)$$

Sensitivity: It represents the rate of true positives.

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5)$$

Specificity: It represents the rate of true negatives.

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (6)$$

F1-score:

It represents the harmonic average of the recall and the precision:

$$F_{score} = 2 * \frac{precision * sensitivity}{precision + sensitivity} \quad (7)$$

A classifier's performance is typically assessed using the confusion matrix. We measure the performance of a classifier based on the measurement criteria that were extracted from this matrix.

In order to complete the evaluation, a number of authors based their work on the overall accuracy, which is a measure of overall performance because it identifies the proportion of all reference sites that have been accurately mapped and measures performance regardless of class size. The overall accuracy is typically expressed as a percentage, and a classification is considered perfect when all the reference sites have been correctly classified when it has a value of 100%.

Two classifiers—the ANN and the KNN—were used in this study to differentiate between individuals without Parkinson's disease (PD) and those who have it. The ANN provides a classification rate of 96.7% and the KNN provides an accuracy of 79.3%, according to the precision classifier.

Existing system:

There are several ways to identify Parkinson's disease symptoms, but most of them call for motor actions that don't show up until the disease has progressed significantly. The most common traditional methods for diagnosing the disease are pricy invasive methods like SPECT and CT tomography, which are primarily effective in the advanced stages of the illness. Apart from conventional approaches, practitioners take a variety of diagnostic routes. Some of them were based on handwriting by taking into account the connection between nervous system issues and handwriting. Others have used peripheral biomarkers to identify PD early.

Proposed system:

A classifier's performance is typically assessed using the confusion matrix. We measure the performance of a classifier based on the measurement criteria that were extracted from this matrix. In order to complete the evaluation, a number of authors based their work on the overall accuracy, which is a measure of overall performance because it identifies the proportion of all reference sites that have been accurately mapped and measures performance regardless of class size. The overall accuracy is typically expressed as a percentage, and a classification is considered perfect when all the reference sites have been correctly classified when it has a value of 100%.

Advantages:

- All voice signals must be measured using both conventional and non-standard measurement techniques in order to calculate the characteristics. For each of the signals, each technique generates a different number.

- The best score was produced by the ANN algorithm. Depending on the data set and the number of acoustic features used, the experiment results showed 96.7% classification accuracy for ANN.

Disadvantages:

- Some of them were based on handwriting by taking into account the connection between nervous system issues and handwriting.
- We must pay close attention to the confusion matrix before defining these criteria. A contingency table is a tool for evaluating how well a learning model performs in classification problems by determining how closely its predictions match the truth.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Deep Learning Solution for Pathological Voice Detection using LSTM-based Autoencoder Hybrid with Multi-Task Learning

Dávid Sztahó, Kiss Gábor and Tulics Miklós Gábrriel proposed To find unreasonable speech disorders, continuous speech is analysed. A hybrid long-short-term memory (LSTM) auto-encoder with multi-task function learning is proposed with spectrogram as an input feature for speech exploitation. To evaluate the suggested DL structure, three datasets were examined. The DL architecture incorporates an LSTM and an auto-encoder. Each database was given a separate train-set, validation-set, and test-set in order to create training, validation, and test sets. A total of ten preparation sets were produced using ten-fold cross-validation (stratified). The minimum cross-entropy of the disease classification served as the study's criterion for determining when to stop early. A maximum of 1000 patience steps were used during the training epochs to avoid early stopping. Training involved the use of the Adam optimizer. Accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were evaluation metrics. As a result, only 76.7% of the test sets can be accurately categorised as healthy or ill.

Deep Learning Approach to Parkinson's Disease Detection Using Voice Recordings and Convolutional Neural Network Dedicated to Image Classification

M. Wodzinski, A. Skalski, D. Hemmerling, J. R. Orozco-Arroyave and E. Nöth, proposed presented a method for treating Parkinson's disease research that relies on vowel sound and is supported by a Res-Net framework initially devoted to image characterization. The time area of the database was significantly increased to prevent over-fitting. There are 100 people in the database (50 of whom are solid and 50 of whom have PD). A slightly modified Res-Net design with 18 layers was used for the auto-encoder, and the final straight layer, which contained a dense network of three layers, was replaced with the P-ReLU as the enactment capacity and function called dropout, which has a probability of 0.5 after the first two layers. The availability of the Image-Net database allowed them to use a pre-trained model, which is the primary reason they chose to use Res-Net. The Image-Net pre-training and dense network layers were used in conjunction with SVD to retrain the entire network. The PD database network was set up in this way with reliable and significant results. Out of a 10-fold validation set of 300 voice recordings, the

framework correctly grouped 275 of them. 85.7% of the recordings were grouped correctly overall.

Improving Parkinson's Disease Diagnosis with Machine Learning Methods

E. Celik and S. I. Omurca, proposed In order to predict Parkinson's disease, a number of classification techniques have been compared, including Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Extra Trees (ET), XGradient Boosting (XGboost), and Random Forest (RF). In this review, a total of 40 people were examined, including 20 PD patients and 20 healthy people. The classification of ML techniques makes use of a sizable collection of speech samples from Parkinson patients. The number of Parkinson's patients was evaluated for the effectiveness of ML techniques in large-scale data problems. The widest feature space and logistic regression yield an accuracy rate of 76.03%. The SVM, with results of 75.49%, produced the best outcomes. In terms of accuracy rates, ET, XGboost, and RT produce the best results with respective accuracy rates of 73.71%, 72.18%, and 71.96%.

Predicting Severity Of Parkinson's Disease Using Deep Learning

Akshama, Abhilasha Yadav, Srishti Grover, Saloni Bhartia, and Seeja K. R proposed The technique uses voice data gathered from the Parkinson's Tele-monitoring speech Database at UCI to predict the severity of Parkinson's disease. To categorise a patient's speech data into "extreme" and "not serious," DL methodology is used to analyse it. The total and motor UPDRS scores were used as evaluation metrics in this exam. The dataset was pre-processed and standardised into a 0–1 scope using min–max (1).

$$\text{Normalized worth of } X = x - \min(x) / \max(x) - \min(x) \quad (1)$$

Here, x = column value, $\min(x)$ = least incentive for that segment and $\max(x)$ = most extreme incentive for that segment.

Ten neurons are found in the first input layer of each of the three hidden layers, followed by ten neurons in the hidden layer and ten neurons in the input layer. UPDRS accuracy to the train and test datasets respectively is 94.4% and 62.7%. Based solely on the Train and Test datasets, Motor UPDRS0's accuracy is 83.3% and 81.6%, respectively. Comparing this proposed DNN model to other existing methods, it was more accurate.

Detecting Parkinson's Disease with Sustained Phonation and Speech Signals using Machine Learning Techniques

Almeida, Jefferson & Filho, Pedro Pedrosa & Pessoa, Tiago & Wei, Wei & Damasevicius, Robertas & Maskeliunas, Rytis & Albuquerque proposed A method that used 18 feature extraction strategies and four machine learning techniques was evaluated in order to categorise the data for the phonation and discourse tasks. In this study, two distinct modalities—phonation and speech—were used. The proposed method for identifying PD relies on motor manifestations that are unmistakably linked to voice. Each sound is examined independently. Two classifiers were discovered to be the most effective ones based on its analysis. Using Phonation (P) sound sort, YA extractor, and K1 classifier, the AC methodology achieved precision of 94.55% and error rate of 19.01%. The SP methodology offers 93.94 percent EER and 92.94% exactness, as well as sound kind (K1) and sound kind (P) extractors. In both the AC and SP methodologies, the implemented methodology produced the best results. The EER for the AC and SP channels were 19.27 percent and 23 percent, respectively, when all capabilities were combined with the current methodology.

A Hybrid Approach to Parkinson Disease Classification Using Speech Signal: The Combination of SMOTE and Random Forests

K. Polat, Proposed a novel method for the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease based on information gleaned from discourse signals. In this paper, several phases of hybrid machine learning are proposed. Data cleaning (oversampling) step one; classification step two. The database (PD database) was taken from the uci ML database and consists of two classes. Using SMOTE and Random Forest classifiers, the study suggests a novel approach for locating an unbalanced distribution of classes in the PD database. The Random Forests classifier's training and testing phases have been separated by 50/50 (or half) and validated ten times, respectively, using a hold-out technique. This technique categorised datasets related to Parkinson's disease using SMOTE and Random-Forests classifiers. In the characterization of the PD dataset, the suggested hybrid strategy (combination of the SMOTE and RT classifiers) had a classification success rate of 94.89%, while the random forest classifier had an accuracy of 86.03%.*Detection of Parkinson's disease from handwriting using deep learning: a comparative study*

Catherine Taleb, Laurence Likforman-Sulem, Chafic Mokbel and Maha Khachab, proposed They studied the application of various DL algorithms, particularly the CNN and the CNN-BLSTM, to detect PD through time series classification. Here is a list of publicly available handwriting datasets by the name of HandPDMultiMC. The feature extractor and the classifier are the two essential components of a CNN model. Two convolution layers, two pooling layers, and an activation function make up each of the

feature extraction layers (ReLU). In the CNN-BLSTM architecture, CNN layers are used for extraction and BLSTMs are used to aid in succession prediction. The best results for early PD recognition on the database come from CNNBLSTM models created with Jittering and Synthetic data augmentation approaches, with a success rate of 96.62%.

Parkinson's Disease Detection from Spiral and Wave Drawings using Convolutional Neural Networks: A Multistage Classifier Approach

S. Chakraborty, S. Aich, Jong-Seong-Sim, E. Han, J. Park and H. -C. Kim proposed The network architecture's spiral and wave drawings are compared to those of Parkinson's disease patients and subjects in good health. To separate the spiral and wave patterns separately, two different kinds of CNNs were used in this methodology. Data was gathered in this case using the Kaggle data archive. Here, a framework is presented to examine how Parkinson's disease (PD) patients identify PD through their spiral and wave drawings. To create 2-D convolutional neural networks, CNN and ensemble classifiers were incorporated into the framework. Expectation probability is trained using a classifier connected to ensemble voting to provide weighted results from both the spirals and waves sketches. The entire model was trained on a total of 55 patients, yielding 93.3 percent success rate, 94 percent recall rate, 93 percent precision, and a 93.4 percent f-1 score.

Classifying Parkinson's Disease Based on Acoustic Measures Using Artificial Neural Networks

Berus, Lucijano, Simon Klancnik, Miran Brezocnik, and Mirko Ficko proposed Parkinson's disease (PD) was predicted using feed-forward artificial neural networks (ANNs) using 26 different voice tests, each of which represented an individual subject's extricated feature. To aid in the calculation process and for data reduction, they have used point selection methods based on principal component analysis, Pearson's correlation coefficient, self-organizing maps, and Kendall's correlation coefficient. To be used in the study, the Parkinson database was retrieved from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. A trained neural network is capable of altering a neuron's weights in a useful way. Scalable conjugate gradient backpropagation is used to achieve this. Because it works well with a scaled-form gradient backpropagation algorithm, the method for preventing over-fitting in this application is terminated early. For A-MCFS (adjusted), Kendall's ANN, PCA-ANN, and self-organizing maps-ANN, there have been 89.43%, 87.51%, 100%, and 100% training accuracy, respectively. The best categorization method for PD determination without maximising component choice methodology has been demonstrated by the combination of different ANNs. Using the neural network, it was finally possible to achieve an accuracy

of 86.47% for the test.

A hybrid system for Parkinson's disease diagnosis using machine learning techniques.

Rohit Lamba, Tarun Gulati, Hadeel Fahad Alharbi and Anurag Jain proposed Speech signals serve as the foundation for the framework's initial analysis, which is intended to help diagnose Parkinson's disease. To achieve this, different associations of feature-selection concepts and classifier algorithms were tested, and the best combinations were used to plan the classification. Three methodological techniques—additional trees, information gain, and genetic algorithms—as well as three classification methods—naive bayes, random forest (RT), and k-nearest neighbour (kNN)—have been used for the analysis of different combinations. With the aid of the speech dataset located in the machine learning repository at UCI, various combinations have been categorised. Given the dataset's unusual imbalance, the synthetic minority oversampling procedure (SMOTE) resolves the class balancing problem. The success rate of the naive bayes classifier was 84.67% using all features and selected subsets of reduced features by feature selection techniques. The kNN classifier performed with an accuracy of 91.45% in an analysis of all features and reduced subsets of features selected by idea called feature selection methods. When applied to all features and reduced feature subsets, a random forest classifier outperforms with a 95.58% accuracy rate.

Parkinson's disease patients classification based on the speech signals

M. Vadovský and J. Paralič proposed The article describes a patient classification system based on speech signals. The algorithms decision tree (DT) classifier, classification and regression trees (CART), and random forest (RT) classifier were used to create the decision trees in the R studio interface. Cut-off values were used for specific attributes in order to further categorise those patients. In this article, information from 40 people was used, half of whom had Parkinson's disease. Each person had multiple records kept of their permanent vowel pronunciations, words, numbers, and sentences. A DT based on the different types of voice signals has been used to create the most accurate classifier model possible. To evaluate how well the models worked, a cross-validation analysis was done. When people said the numbers aloud, a relatively higher average success rate of 66.5 percent was attained.

Hyper-parameter optimization of deep learning model for prediction of Parkinson's disease.

Kaur, S., Aggarwal, H. and Rani, R proposed An optimization framework for grid-search is suggested in order to implement a deep learning-DL framework that can predict the occurrence of parkinson's disease in its early stages. This framework is set with multiple hyperparameters and tunes them for evaluation of

the DL model. The topology of the DL model, hyperparameters, and performance are the three steps in the optimization process for the grid search. Data used in this computation was obtained from the UCI machine learning archive and used in the grid search. By contrasting voice samples from PD patients and healthy individuals, the developed concept is evaluated. With the help of grid-search hyper-parameter tuning, this improved classification precision was attained with an overall accuracy of 89.23% and a mean of 91.69% for the DL model. Here, a technique for early Parkinson's disease prediction is presented.

Parkinson's Disease Diagnosis in Cepstral Domain Using MFCC and Dimensionality Reduction with SVM Classifier.

Rahman, Atiqur & Rizvi, Dr. Sanam & Khan, Aurangzeb & Abbasi, Aaqif & Khan, Shafqatullah & Chung, Tae-Sun Proposed Cepstral features can be extracted and analysed using voice data recorded from people with Parkinson's disease (PD) and from people in good health to detect PD. To reduce the dimensionality of the extracted features, it is advised that linear discriminant analysis use a support vector machine classifier as a classification algorithm. The development of ten different machine learning techniques served to further validate the developed method. This results in an AUC of about 88 percent, a specificity of 84 percent, and a sensitivity of 73.33 percent for the developed method. In a subsequent step, the proposed intelligent system was simulated using open databases that contain a variety of voices. The survey included patients from inside and outside the state. When compared to earlier studies, the results from the public database are encouraging.

Freezing of Gait (FoG) Detection Using Logistic Regression in Parkinson's Disease from Acceleration Signals

K. Polat proposed To determine whether people with Parkinson's disease experience gait freezing, the logistic regression (LR) model was examined (FoG). Patients in this study were initially fitted with acceleration sensors in order to gather information. Additionally, using the Fast Fourier Transform, features have been extracted from these acceleration signals (FFT). The coefficient frequency is calculated using these acceleration signals and the FFT concept. These signals have undergone statistical analysis to determine standard deviation, maximum and minimum amplitudes, maximum and minimum energies, and standard forms of each in order to reduce the number of features. For each class, the following five variables were taken (three for FoG and three for non-FoG). There are 8 patients with PD disorder in the dataset. Based on the dataset's extracted features, the gait frozen cases were identified using logistic regression modelling. Classifying FoG cases using acceleration signals resulted in an accuracy of 81.30

percent. Four additional classifiers were used in addition to logistic regression to categorise FoG cases. Based on the findings of the study, the proposed method was shown to be successful in identifying and diagnosing parkinson's disease.

Wrist Sensor Based Tremor Diagnosis In Parkinson's Disease Using Machine Learning Algorithm

Prema Arokia Mary G, Suganthi N, Monisha M, Ragapriyaa C and Vignesh N proposed The accelerometer device, which can detect tremor, has been used to develop a wearable device for measuring tremor. A list of the tremors found is compiled using accelerometers and gyroscopes. To train, examine, and determine the severity of a disease, the extreme gradient boosting algorithm is used (PD). The base learner in this algorithm is a decision tree. In this study, Naive Bayes classification was used in addition to KNN (k-nearest neighbours). This model generates a 94.87% accurate result that enables a patient to get in touch with the hospital if they experience tremor. Naive Bayes generates a result of 91%, while KNN (k-nearest neighbours) generates an outcome of 90%.

Predicting Metamorphic Changes in Parkinson's Disease Patients Using Machine Learning Algorithms

G.Prema Arokia Mary proposed ML techniques are suggested as a methodology for determining the percentage of unstable changes in a Parkinson's patient. From PPMI, a dataset has been extracted. The effects of PD patients' daily activities are evaluated using this database. Recurrent neural networks, logistic regression, and principal component analysis are the three algorithms that are used for predictions. The steps in the above methodology are data pre-processing, data separation into training sets and testing sets, implementation of the prediction algorithm, performance assessment using the metrics accuracy, recall, precision, and f1-score calculation. When compared to PCA algorithm and RNN algorithm, which produce accuracy of 83% and 89% for the sleep dataset respectively and an outcome of 80% and 86% for Olfactory (smell) dataset, respectively, logistic regression can predict metamorphic changes with 92% accuracy for the sleep dataset and 95% accuracy for the olfactory (smell) dataset.

Multiple-Fine-Tuned Convolutional Neural Networks for Parkinson's Disease Diagnosis From Offline Handwriting

M. Gazda, M. Hireš and P. Drotár proposed This paper presents a method for diagnosing Parkinson's disease (PD) from handwriting images using a convolutional neural network (CNN) without the use of any additional signals. Therefore, no specialised hardware or feature engineering is required. It was

suggested to fine-tune CNN more than once in order to improve its performance. The source database and target database must be able to fill the semantic gap for transfer learning to be successful. Here, two datasets are utilised. Weights are built with which CNNs are constructed by training multiple fine-tuning techniques in a CNN ensemble. A CNN ensemble is then produced by combining these weights. A suggested architecture can identify PD from offline handwriting with 94.7% accuracy by combining several fine-tuned CNNs.

A Novel Ensemble of Random Forest for Assisting Diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease on Small Handwritten Dynamics Dataset

Xu S, Pan Z, proposed An ensemble learning model using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Random Forest (RF) techniques is presented to investigate whether PD patients have a higher risk of developing Parkinson's disease than healthy controls. In order to obtain the corresponding class probability vectors, six different handwritten exams were used to construct six different RF methods. Voting was a method used to obtain a single prediction result for each RF model. Performance evaluation of the classifier was carried out using K-fold cross validation on the exam datasets. The ensemble model performs better at classifying six handwritten exams than RF. The ensemble with RF model's accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, and F1-score for multiple handwriting tests are 89.4%, 93.7%, 84.5%, and 87.7%, respectively. SVM and Logistic-Regression are frequently outperformed by ensemble models developed using RF.

Deep Convolutional Neural Network for Parkinson's Disease Based Handwriting Screening

M. Shaban proposed Based on a Kaggle handwriting database, a modified version of the VGG-19 is researched and tested for diagnosing Parkinson's disease (PD). The database contains 102 wave drawing patterns and 102 spiral sketching patterns. To reduce over-fitting, an image augmentation method was used. With a 4fold and 10fold cross-validation, a convolutional neural network (CNN) was trained using the pre-processed database. The success rates for the wave drawing pattern, spiral drawing pattern, and 10x cross validation process for the CNN architecture were 88%, 89%, and 87%, respectively. The suggested method for PD screening and assessment based on handwriting patterns presents a promising alternative to the cutting-edge architecture that makes use of a finely tuned AlexNet model.

Classification of Parkinson's Disease using Speech Attributes with Parametric and Nonparametric Machine Learning Techniques

S. Sharanyaa, P. N. Renjith and K. Ramesh proposed Make a distinction between Parkinson's disease and dysphonic speech disorder based on the acoustic characteristics of Parkinson's disorder patients' voices. Machine learning methods, including parametric and nonparametric ones, were used to analyse the voice feature dataset. The effectiveness of various ideas, including Random Forest-(RT), Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Logistic Regression-(LR) Algorithm, is assessed using this technique. On the basis of speech attributes, pre-processed data is fed into machine learning models. For each of the four ML techniques, performance metrics such as recall, precision, and F1 score are calculated. Nonparametric models using K-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) and Random Forest (RF) outperform parametric models in categorization with 87.2% and 90.2% accuracy, respectively.

CHAPTER 3

PARKINSON'S DISEASE

Parkinson's disease (PD), also known as Parkinson's, or just Parkinson's [10], is a chronic degenerative disorder of the central nervous system that primarily affects the motor system. Typically, symptoms appear gradually, and as the condition worsens, non-motor symptoms increase in frequency. [1] [5] Tremor, rigidity, slowness of movement, and difficulty walking are the most noticeable early symptoms. In addition to behavioural and cognitive issues, many people with Parkinson's disease experience depression, anxiety, and apathy. [11] As the disease progresses, dementia caused by Parkinson's disease becomes more prevalent. Parkinson's patients may also experience issues with their sleep and sensory systems. [1] [2] The disease's motor symptoms are caused by a dopamine deficit brought on by cell death in the substantia nigra, a midbrain region. [1] Although the exact cause of this cell death is unknown, it appears that misfolded proteins accumulate in the form of Lewy bodies in the neurons. [12] [5] The primary motor symptoms are collectively referred to as parkinsonism or a parkinsonian syndrome. [5]

Although the exact cause of PD is unknown, it is thought that both inherited and environmental factors may be involved. Certain genes are known to be inheritable risk factors for the disease, which increases the risk for those who have a family member with the disease. People who have been exposed to specific pesticides and those who have suffered head injuries in the past are also at risk. Smokers, tea drinkers, and coffee drinkers all have a lower risk.

Symptoms, particularly motor symptoms, are the primary basis for diagnosis in typical cases. To help rule out other diseases, tests like neuroimaging (such as magnetic resonance imaging or imaging to look at dopamine neuronal dysfunction known as a DaT scan) can be used. [15] [1] About 1% of people over the age of 60 who have Parkinson's disease experience it on a regular basis. [1] [4] Males are affected more frequently than females, roughly 3:2. [5] Early-onset PD is the term used to describe it when it affects people under the age of 50. [16] By 2015, PD had killed about 117,400 people worldwide and affected 6.2 million people. [8] [9] After diagnosis, the typical life expectancy ranges from 7 to 15 years.

Treatment for PD aims to lessen the effects of the symptoms as there is no known cure. Levodopa (L-DOPA), MAO-B inhibitors, or dopamine agonists are frequently used as the first line of treatment for Parkinson's disease. These drugs produce a side effect known as involuntary muscle movements, but as

the disease worsens, they become less effective.

At that point, medication combinations and dose adjustments are both possible. Diet and some rehabilitation techniques have shown some promise in improving symptoms. In severe cases where medications are ineffective, surgery to implant microelectrodes for deep brain stimulation has been used to lessen motor symptoms. [1] Less convincing evidence supports treatments for PD symptoms other than movement, like sleep issues and emotional issues.

The condition bears the name James Parkinson after the English physician who wrote the first in-depth account of it in *An Essay on the Shaking Palsy* in 1817. Public awareness campaigns include the use of a red tulip as the disease symbol and World Parkinson's Day (April 11, the birthday of James Parkinson). Boxer Muhammad Ali, comedian Billy Connolly, actor Michael J. Fox, Olympic cyclist Davis Phinney, and actor Alan Alda are all PD patients who have helped raise awareness of the illness.

Classification:

The most prevalent type of parkinsonism, known as "idiopathic parkinsonism," or parkinsonism without a known cause, is Parkinson's disease. [17] [27] Because of an abnormal buildup of the protein alpha-synuclein in the brain, it is sometimes referred to as a type of neurodegenerative disease called synucleinopathy. [28] The classification of synucleinopathy sets it apart from neurodegenerative conditions like Alzheimer's disease, in which the brain builds up a different protein called tau protein. [28]

Tauopathies and synucleinopathies share a great deal of clinical and pathological similarities, but they also differ. Memory loss is a common symptom of Alzheimer's disease, as opposed to Parkinson's disease (PD). Slowness, tremor, stiffness, and postural instability, which are the four hallmarks of Parkinson's disease, are not typical symptoms of Alzheimer's.

There have been attempts to categorise PD into various subtypes, focusing on the age at onset, the progression of symptoms, and the dominance of tremor, but none have been accepted.

Signs and symptoms:

The movement (motor)-related early symptoms are the most noticeable. [32] Non-motor symptoms, such

as autonomic dysfunction (dysautonomia), neuropsychiatric issues (mood, cognition, behaviour, or thought changes), sensory symptoms (particularly an altered sense of smell), and sleep problems, are typically associated with later stages but may be present at the time of diagnosis.

Motor :

In Parkinson's disease (PD), tremor, bradykinesia (slowness of movement), rigidity, and postural instability are regarded as the four cardinal motor symptoms. The most typical presenting symptom is a coarse, slow tremor in the hand when it is at rest. This tremor goes away when the affected arm is moved voluntarily and during deeper stages of sleep.

Usually affecting only one hand at first, the disease eventually spreads to both hands. The PD tremor frequency ranges from 4 to 6 hertz (cycles per second). The tendency of the thumb and index finger to touch and move in unison in a circular motion is known as pill-rolling, which is a symptom of tremor. The phrase "PD movement" refers to the movement of people who have the disorder and the early pharmaceutical practise of manually making pills.

Every case of PD exhibits bradykinesia, which results from problems with motor planning of movement initiation and is accompanied by challenges throughout the entire movement process, from planning to initiation to execution. Performance of sequential and simultaneous movement is impaired. The most challenging Parkinson's disease symptom, bradykinesia, makes it difficult to perform basic daily tasks like dressing, eating, and bathing. It makes it particularly difficult to perform two independent motor tasks at once, and emotional stress or concurrent illnesses can make it worse. Contrary to popular belief, people with PD frequently find it easier to ride a bike or climb stairs than to walk on a level surface. While the majority of doctors can easily detect bradykinesia, a formal assessment requires subjects to perform repetitive foot and finger movements.

Rigidity, or increased muscle tone, is a stiffness and resistance to limb movement brought on by an excessive and ongoing contraction of the muscles. Lead-pipe rigidity or cogwheel rigidity are two different types of rigidity that can occur in parkinsonism. The cause of cogwheel rigidity is thought to be the interaction of tremor and elevated tone. Joint pain is frequently the first symptom of the disease and may be linked to rigidity. Early on in Parkinson's disease, rigidity is frequently asymmetrical and affects the muscles of the neck and shoulders before the muscles of the face and extremities. [38] Rigidity typically worsens with disease progression and impairs mobility throughout the entire body.

In the later stages of the illness, postural instability is common, which causes impaired balance and frequent falls as well as bone fractures, a loss of confidence, and restricted mobility. In the beginning, especially in younger people, and especially before the onset of bilateral symptoms, instability is frequently absent. Up to 40% of those with PD may experience falls, and 10% may experience falls on a weekly basis. The severity of PD is correlated with the number of falls.

Gait and posture issues like festination are among the other recognised motor signs and symptoms (rapid shuffling steps and a forward-flexed posture when walking with no flexed arm swing). Other common symptoms include a slurred, monotonous voice, a mask-like expression, and shrinking handwriting. Freezing of gait (brief arrests when the feet seem to get stuck to the floor, especially on turning or changing direction) is another common symptom.

Neuropsychiatric :

Neuropsychiatric disturbances caused by PD range in severity from mild to severe. They cover mental, emotional, behavioural, and cognitive disorders. Cognitive disturbances can start in the early stages of the disease or even before a diagnosis is made, and their frequency rises as the illness progresses. Executive dysfunction, which includes issues with planning, cognitive flexibility, abstract thinking, rule acquisition, inhibiting inappropriate actions, starting appropriate actions, working memory, and attention control, is the most prevalent cognitive deficit. [43][44] Slowed cognitive processing speed, poor memory, and poor perception and time estimation are some other cognitive issues. Nevertheless, when recall is aided by cues, improvement is seen. Visual processing issues are another aspect of the illness, as demonstrated, for instance, when the patient is asked to complete tests of facial recognition and orientation perception of drawn lines.

In comparison to the general population, PD patients have a two to six times higher risk of developing dementia. Up to 78% of Parkinson's disease (PD) patients also have dementia. Age and, to a lesser extent, disease duration both affect dementia prevalence. [46] Dementia is linked to decreased quality of life for people with Parkinson's disease (PD) and those who care for them, higher mortality rates, and a higher likelihood of needing nursing home care.

Medication, especially orally active dopamine agonists, can lead to impulse-control disorders, such as pathological gambling, compulsive sexual behaviour, binge eating, compulsive shopping, and reckless

generosity. A rare side effect of taking levodopa is the dopamine dysregulation syndrome, in which a lack of medication results in overuse.

Another issue brought on by anti-Parkinson medication is pounding, which consists of complex, monotonous, aimless, stereotyped behaviours that last for many hours.

Psychosis :

The prevalence of psychosis can be thought of as a symptom, with a wide range from 26 to 83%. [11] [48] About 50% of PD patients experience hallucinations or delusions over the course of their illness, which may signal the beginning of dementia. These can range in severity from mild sense of passage (something quickly passing beside the person) or sense of presence (the perception of something or someone standing just to the side or behind the person) to fully formed, vivid visual hallucinations and paranoid ideation.

A rare occurrence in PD, auditory hallucinations are rarely described as voices. The disease is now thought to include psychosis as a core component. A psychosis with delusions and accompanying delirium is a known side effect of anti-Parkinson drug therapy and may also be brought on by urinary tract infections (as frequently happens in frail elderly patients), but medications and infections are not the only causes of psychosis in PD; other potential causes include underlying brain pathology or changes in neurotransmitters or their receptors (e.g., acetylcholine, serotonin).

Behavior and mood :

Alterations in behaviour and mood are more prevalent than in the general population in PD without cognitive impairment and are typically present in PD with dementia. The most common mood problems are anxiety, apathy, and depression.

According to estimates, depression can manifest at any stage of the disease in 20 to 35% of people with Parkinson's disease. It can present with symptoms that are typical of the disease process (fatigue, insomnia, and concentration problems), making diagnosis challenging. Dopamine, serotonin, and noradrenergic hormone imbalances and changes are well known to be a major contributor to depression in PD patients. Functional impairment brought on by the disease is another factor. Loss of interest, sadness, guilt, feelings of helplessness, hopelessness, and guilt, as well as suicidal thoughts, are all possible symptoms of depression. Suicidal ideation is more prevalent in PD patients than in the general population,

but actual suicide attempts are less frequent than in patients with depression who do not have PD. Being a woman, having experienced depression in the past, having severe motor symptoms, and other factors can all be risk factors for depression in people with Parkinson's disease.

According to estimates, anxiety affects 30–40% (up to 60%) of people with Parkinson's disease (PD). Often, anxiety is present when things are going wrong (times when medication is not working as well as it did before). Panic attacks happen more frequently in people with PD than in the general population. It has been discovered that lower quality of life is linked to both depression and anxiety. Potential causes of symptoms include abnormal gamma-aminobutyric acid levels, embarrassment or fear over symptoms or illness, and they can be mild, episodic, or chronic. Disease onset before the age of 50, women, and rest periods are risk factors for anxiety in PD.

Loss of motivation and a lowered capacity for enjoyment are two terms that describe apathy and anhedonia, respectively. They are traditional depression symptoms, but in PD patients, their treatment and mechanism vary, and they don't always accompany depression. Around 16.5 to 40% of people exhibit apathy. Reduced initiative or interest in new endeavours or the environment, emotional indifference, and a loss of affection or concern for others are all signs of apathy. Cognitive deficits, including those in verbal and executive memory, are linked to apathy.

Other :

The disease's characteristic sleep disorders can be made worse by medication. [32] Drowsiness during the day (including sudden sleep attacks resembling narcolepsy), problems with rapid eye movement sleep, or insomnia are all possible symptoms. [32] REM behaviour disorder may start many years before the onset of the motor or cognitive symptoms of Parkinson's disease (PD) or dementia with Lewy bodies. In this condition, people act out their dreams and may occasionally hurt themselves or their bed partner.

Orthostatic hypotension (low blood pressure when standing up), oily skin, excessive sweating, urinary incontinence, and altered sexual function are all symptoms of autonomic nervous system changes. Severe constipation and poor stomach emptying (gastric dysmotility) can be uncomfortable and even dangerous to one's health.

Perceptual changes can affect one's ability to smell, see clearly, feel pain, and experience paresthesia

(tingling and numbness). Years may pass before the disease is identified by any one of these symptoms.

Causes :

Numerous risk factors have been put forth, some in connection with theories about potential disease mechanisms, but none have been proven beyond a reasonable doubt. [54] The most frequently observed associations are an increased risk in pesticide users and a decreased risk in smokers. [54] [55] There may be a connection between PD and the *Helicobacter pylori* infection, which can impair levodopa absorption among other medications.

Figure 1: Parkin Crystal Structure

Genetic :

According to research, complex interactions between genetic and environmental factors result in PD. [5] A first-degree relative with Parkinson's disease affects about 15% of those who have it [17], and mutations in one of several specific genes are known to cause the disease in 5–10% of PD patients. [58] [59] Even if a person carries one of these gene mutations, they may not develop the disease; however, they are more likely to do so if they also have other risk factors, which also affect the disease's age of onset, severity, and progression. [58] The development of PD has been linked to at least 11 autosomal dominant and 9 autosomal recessive gene mutations. SNCA, PARK3, UCHL1, LRRK2, GIGYF2, HTRA2, EIF4G1, TMEM230, CHCHD2, RIC3, and VPS35 are among the autosomal dominant genes. PRKN, PINK1, PARK7, ATP13A2, PLA2G6, FBXO7, DNAJC6, SYNJ1, and VPS13C are autosomal recessive genes. PARK10, PARK12, and PARK16 are examples of genes with an X-linked inheritance pattern or an ambiguous inheritance pattern. The deletion of 22q11 has also been linked to PD.

Mutations in the LRP10 gene have been linked to an autosomal dominant form. The GBA1 gene has mutations in about 5% of PD patients. Less than 1% of the population who are unaffected has these mutations. If these mutations exist, there is a 20–30 fold increase in the risk of developing PD. The clinical characteristics of PD associated with these mutations are the same, but the onset age and rate of cognitive and motor decline are earlier. Glucocerebrosidase is encoded by this gene. Gaucher's disease is caused by low levels of this enzyme.

Because the protein that this gene encodes, alpha-synuclein, is a key component of the Lewy bodies that build up in the brains of people with PD, SNCA gene mutations are significant in the disease.

Ataxia Telangiectasia Mutated is a key DNA damage-repair signalling kinase that is activated by alpha-synuclein. [63] Alpha-synuclein also stimulates the pathway for non-homologous end joining DNA repair. Reduced DNA repair and brain cell death in Parkinson's disease (PD) seem to be connected by the accumulation of alpha-synuclein in Lewy bodies.

There have been discoveries that certain gene mutations, such as those in the SNCA, LRRK2, and GBA, are risk factors for sporadic (nonfamilial) PD.

The most frequent known cause of familial and sporadic PD is mutations in the LRRK2 gene, which account for about 5% of people with a family history of the condition and 3% of sporadic cases. The greatest genetic risk factor for Parkinson's disease is a mutation in GBA.

Lysosomes, which are organelles that break down cellular waste, function in part thanks to several genes associated with Parkinson's disease. Lysosomal diseases that impair cells' capacity to break down alpha-synuclein may contribute to some cases of Parkinson's disease (PD).

Non-genetic:

Both pesticide exposure and a history of head injuries have been connected to PD, but the risks are low. A slight increase in the risk of developing PD is also linked to never drinking caffeine-containing beverages. [47] Manganese and carbon disulfide are two toxins that can lead to Parkinson's disease.

prescription drugs linked to cases of parkinsonism. By stopping the offending substance, such as

phenothiazines (chlorpromazine, promazine, etc.); butyrophenones (haloperidol, benperidol, etc.); metoclopramide and Tetrabenazine, drug-induced parkinsonism is typically reversible. Animal models are frequently used in research thanks to the drug 1-Methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP), which is known for causing irreversible parkinsonism.

An increased risk of PD is linked to low blood urate concentrations.

Infections and abnormal metabolic processes are two additional recognised causes of parkinsonism. Atypical parkinsonism and parkinson plus syndromes are names for a number of neurodegenerative conditions that can also manifest as parkinsonism (illnesses with parkinsonism plus some other features distinguishing them from PD). They include dementia with Lewy bodies, corticobasal degeneration, progressive supranuclear palsy, and multiple system atrophy. [17] [74] Another synucleinopathy is dementia with Lewy bodies, and it shares many pathological features with PD, particularly with the subset of PD cases with dementia known as Parkinson's disease dementia. The connection between PD and DLB is convoluted and understudied. [75] They could be components of a continuum with distinct clinical and pathological characteristics, or they could turn out to be distinct diseases. [75]

The phenomenon of having both vascular events and Parkinson's disease symptoms is known as vascular parkinsonism (such as a cerebral stroke). Both vascular parkinsonism and idiopathic PD have similar causes—damage to the dopaminergic pathways—and can exhibit many of the same symptoms. Imaging, history analysis, and a careful bedside examination can all be used to differentiate.

Diagnosis:

A thorough medical history and neurological examination are the first steps in a doctor's evaluation of Parkinson's disease (PD)[32]. Motor symptoms like bradykinesia and rest tremor are confirmed, and tests are supported by clinical diagnostic criteria. Lewy bodies in the midbrain discovered during an autopsy are typically regarded as definitive evidence that the patient had PD. It is necessary to periodically review the clinical presentation to confirm the accuracy of the diagnosis because the clinical course of the illness over time may reveal it is not PD.[32][85]

The causes of Parkinson's disease and diseases with similar symptoms can vary. Parkinson-plus syndromes, such as progressive supranuclear palsy and multiple system atrophy, must also be considered

and appropriately ruled out due to different treatment and disease progression (anti-medication Parkinson's are typically less effective at controlling symptoms in Parkinson-plus syndromes).[32] Faster progression rates, early cognitive impairment, and other factors all require consideration .[86]

To facilitate and standardise the diagnostic process, particularly in the early stages of the disease, medical organisations have developed diagnostic criteria. The UK's Queen Square Brain Bank for Neurological Disorders and the United States are the sources of the most well-known criteria. Stroke and Neurological Disorders National Institute. The Queen Square Brain Bank criteria call for rigidity, resting tremor, or postural instability in addition to slowness of movement (bradykinesia). There must be a rule out for other potential causes of these symptoms. Last but not least, at least three of the supporting characteristics listed below must be present during the onset or evolution of the condition: unilateral onset, tremor at rest, progression over time, asymmetry of motor symptoms, response to levodopa for at least five years, clinical course lasting at least ten years, and emergence of dyskinesias brought on by excessive levodopa intake. [87] Evaluation of sudomotor function through electrochemical skin conductance can be helpful in diagnosis .[88]

When PD diagnoses are verified by autopsy, movement disorders specialists' initial diagnoses are on average 79.6% accurate and their refined diagnoses at follow-up exams are 83.9% accurate. The average accuracy is 73.8% when clinical diagnoses made primarily by non-experts are verified by autopsy. Overall, 82.7% of diagnoses made using the Brain Bank criteria and 80.6% of diagnoses made for PD are correct.

Figure 2: An Illustration of the dopamine pathways throughout the brain

Imaging :

People with Parkinson's disease (PD) typically have normal computed tomography (CT) scans.[90] Magnetic resonance imaging has improved over time in diagnosing the disease, particularly through iron-sensitive T2* and susceptibility weighted imaging sequences at a magnetic field strength of at least 3T, both of which can show absence of the recognisable "swallow tail" imaging pattern in the dorsolateral substantia nigra .[90]

Positron emission tomography and single-photon emission computed tomography scans can be used to directly measure the metabolic activity of dopamine transporters in the basal ganglia; the DaTSCAN is a popular proprietary version of this research. Reduced basal ganglia dopamine-related activity can help rule out Parkinsonism brought on by drugs. It has demonstrated high agreement with clinical diagnoses of Parkinsonism. In the United States, DaTSCANS are only FDA approved to distinguish PD or Parkinsonian syndromes from essential tremor. This finding is not completely specific, though, and can be seen with both PD and Parkinson-plus disorders .[96]

Finding denervation of the heart's surrounding muscles with iodine-123-meta-iodobenzylguanidine myocardial scintigraphy can assist in making the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.

Differential diagnosis:

Secondary parkinsonism - With careful history-taking, a thorough physical examination, and the appropriate imaging, the various causes of parkinsonism can be distinguished from one another. [68] [15][97] The causes section of this page goes into more detail on this subject.

Figure 3: Hot Cross Bun sign that is commonly found in MRI of Multiple System Atrophy

Parkinson's disease plus The Parkinson's plus group of illnesses includes a variety of conditions like corticobasal syndrome, multiple system atrophy, progressive supranuclear palsy, and dementia with lewy bodies. A thorough history and physical examination that is focused on the onset of particular symptoms, the course of the disease, and the patient's response to treatment can help narrow the differential diagnosis. [98][97] The main differences between them.

Multiple system atrophy – levodopa resistance, rapidly progressive, autonomic failure, stridor, present Babinski sign, cerebellar ataxia, and specific MRI findings

Corticobasal syndrome – levodopa-resistance, myoclonus, dystonia, corticostimulatory loss, apraxia, and non-fluent aphasia

Dementia with Lewy bodies – levodopa resistance, cognitive predominance before motor symptoms, and fluctuating cognitive symptoms, (visual hallucinations are very common in this disease, but PD patients also have them)

Progressive supranuclear palsy – levodopa resistance, restrictive vertical gaze, specific MRI findings, and early and different postural difficulties

Essential tremor – This can at first look like parkinsonism, but has key differentiators. In essential tremor, the tremor gets worse with action (whereas in PD, it gets better), a lack of other symptoms is common in PD, and normal DatSCAN is seen.

Other conditions that can have similar presentations to PD include:

- Arthritis
- Creutzfeldt–Jakob disease
- Dystonia
- Depression
- Fragile X-associated tremor/ataxia syndrome
- Frontotemporal dementia and parkinsonism linked to chromosome 17
- Huntington's disease
- Idiopathic basal ganglia calcification
- Neurodegeneration with brain iron accumulation
- Normal-pressure hydrocephalus
- Obsessional slowness
- Psychogenic parkinsonism
- Wilson's disease

History:

Early sources that describe symptoms similar to those of PD include an Egyptian papyrus, an Ayurvedic medical treatise, the Bible, and Galen's writings. [158] The first references to PD after Galen don't appear until the 17th century. [158] In the 17th and 18th centuries, authors like Sylvius, Gaubius, Hunter, and Chomel wrote about various aspects of the illness. James Parkinson, an English physician, published an essay in 1817 detailing six cases of paralysis agitans.

An Essay on the Shaking Palsy discussed the disease's progressive nature, the recognisable resting tremor, abnormal posture and gait, paralysis, and diminished muscle strength. Trousseau, Gowers, Kinnier

Wilson, and Erb were early neurologists who contributed to the understanding of the illness, but most notably Jean-Martin Charcot, whose research between 1868 and 1881 was a turning point in the understanding of the illness. [22] He introduced the distinction between rigidity, weakness, and bradykinesia, among other innovations. [22] He also promoted renaming the illness in James Parkinson's honour.

Frederic Lewy first described the tiny particles in affected brains in 1912; these were later referred to as Lewy bodies.

Konstantin Tretiakoff stated in 1919 that the substantia nigra was the primary affected cerebral structure, but this conclusion was not widely accepted until it was supported by additional research published by Rolf Hassler in 1938. Due in large part to the research of Arvid Carlsson on the neurotransmitter dopamine and Oleh Hornykiewicz on its impact on Parkinson's disease (PD), the underlying biochemical changes in the brain were discovered in the 1950s. [162] Alpha-synuclein was discovered by Spillantini, Trojanowski, Goedert, and others to be the primary component of Lewy bodies in 1997.

Until the introduction of levodopa, the only treatments were anticholinergics and surgery (lesioning of the corticospinal pathway or some of the basal ganglia structures). Casimir Funk created levodopa for the first time in 1911, but it wasn't widely studied until the middle of the 20th century. [162] It revolutionised the way PD was managed when it was introduced to clinical practise. [162] [164] As a potential therapy, deep brain stimulation was introduced by Alim Louis Benabid and colleagues in Grenoble, France, in the late 1980s.

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY

The Parkinson's UI Machine Learning [4] database, which has acoustic characteristics, is the foundation of the current study.

A. Dataset:

The database includes 195 recordings of sustained vocal phonations from 31 male and female subjects, 23 of whom had Parkinson's disease. Patients range in age from 46 to 85 years old (average of 65.8, standard deviation of 9.8). A total of six phonations, averaging six seconds each, were recorded for each patient.

This database states that the main objective is to separate healthy individuals from those who have Parkinson's disease. Based on the "status" column, which has a value of 0 for healthy individuals and 1 for PD patients, the decision is made. Each line in the table corresponds to one of the 195 recordings of these people's voices, and each column in the table represents a measure of voice (the column "name").

B. Speech recordings:

Ages of the subjects ranged from 46 to 85 years old (average of 65.8 and standard deviation of 9.8). Six phonations with average durations ranging from 1 to 36 seconds were recorded for each subject. For subject information, see Table I. Plots of two of these voice signals are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Example of speech signal of a healthy individual

Figure 5: Example of speech signal of a subject with PD

The phonations were captured using an AKG C420 head-mounted microphone placed 8 cm away from the lips in an Industrial Acoustics Company (IAC) sound-treated booth. A class 1 sound-level metre (B&K 2238) placed 30 cm from the speaker was used to calibrate the microphone. The voice signals were directly recorded onto the computer using Computerized Speech Laboratory (CSL) 4300B hardware (KAY Elemetrics), sampled at 44.1 kHz with 16-bit resolution.

C. Feature Extraction / Selection :

All voice signals must be measured using both conventional and non-standard measurement techniques in order to calculate the characteristics. For each of the 195 signals, each technique generates a different number. A list of the measurements that made up this study's characteristics can be found in Table 2.

Calculation of traditional measures

Software from Praat was used to perform this calculation [6]. Traditional measurements are based on applying short-term autocorrelation to successive segments of the signal, with peak peaking to determine the frequency of the vocal cords' vibration (F_0 or pitch period), and the precise moment when each cycle of the vocal cords' vibration began (pitch marks).

Table Head	Table Column Head
MDVP : F0 (Hz)	Average vocal fundamental frequency
MDVP : Fhi (Hz)	Maximum vocal fundamental frequency
MDVP : Flo (Hz)	Minimum vocal fundamental frequency
MDVP : Jitter (%)	Fundamental frequency perturbation (%)
MDVP : Jitter (Abs)	Absolute jitter in microseconds
MDVP : RAP	Relative Amplitude Perturbation
MDVP : PPQ	Five-point Period Perturbation Quotient
Jitter : DDP	Average absolute difference of differences between cycles, divided by the average
MDVP : Shimmer	periodShimmer Local amplitude perturbation
MDVP: Shimmer (db)	Local amplitude perturbation (decibels)
Shimmer : APQ3	3-point Amplitude Perturbation Quotient
Shimmer : APQ5	5-point Amplitude Perturbation Quotient
MDVP : APQ	11-point Amplitude Perturbation Quotient
Shimmer : DDA	Average absolute difference between the amplitudes of consecutive periods
NHR	Noise-to-Harmonics Ratio
HNR	Harmonics-to-Noise Ratio
RPDE	Recurrence Period Density Entropy
D2	Correlation Dimension
DFA	Detrended Fluctuation Analysis
Spread1	Fundamental frequency variation
Spread2	Fundamental frequency variation
PPE	Pitch period entropy

Table 2: ATTRIBUTE DETAILS FOR DIAGNOSIS OF PD PATIENT

It is necessary to use the sequence of frequencies for each vocal cycle in order to calculate the jitter and period disturbance measurements. This is done by taking the successive absolute differences between each cycle's frequencies and calculating the average over a range of cycles before finally normalising by the overall average.

The maximum extent of the amplitude of the signal within each vocal cycle is used to determine the shimmer and amplitude perturbation measures. This sequence's average difference is used to calculate the

variation in cycle amplitudes. The signal-to-noise estimates of each cycle's autocorrelation are used to determine the noise-to-harmonics (and harmonics-to-noise) ratios. Refer to [6], [8], and [7] for more information on how to calculate the traditional measures.

Calculation of Nonstandard measures:

In order to reconstruct the phase space of the nonlinear dynamical system and produce the speech signal, the correlation dimension (D2) is calculated based on time-delay embedding of the signal [10]. A geometrically self-similar (fractal) object was used to represent complex dynamics that are implicated in dysphonia in this recreation phase space [9]. We use the implementation of Time Series Analysis (TISEAN) [11]. The degree to which dynamics in the reconstructed phase space after time-delay embedding can be viewed as strictly periodic, that is, repeating exactly, is quantified by the recurrence period density entropy (RPDE) [13].

A recurrent signal with the recurrence period T periodically returns to the same location in the phase space. It has been demonstrated that the entropy H of the distribution of these recurrence periods accurately measures the deviation from periodicity. $P(T)$ is a useful indicator of general voice disorders because general voice pathologies point to a decrease in the ability of the vocal folds to sustain regular vibration [13]. By dividing the RPDE values (H_{norm}) by the entropy of the uniform distribution, to the range $[0,1]$, the values are normalised.

Finally, DFA measures how much the noise in the speech signal is stochastically self-similar. Speech noise is primarily produced by turbulent airflow through the vocal folds [13]. It has been observed that for general voice disorders, dysphonic subjects have a larger scaling exponent than healthy subjects [8]. The DFA algorithm determines how much the speech signal's amplitude varies $F(L)$ over a variety of time scales. Additionally, the slope of a straight line on a log-log plot of L versus $F(L)$ is used to determine the self-similarity of the speech signal. The slope values (norm) are then normalised to the range $[0, 1]$ using a straightforward nonlinear transformation. [8].

Classifiers baselines:

K-nearest neighbours and artificial neural networks (ANN) are the machine learning algorithms used in our study (KNN). They rank among the most well-liked literary classifications. Each of them has unique tuning methods and techniques that will be used to distinguish PD patients from healthy individuals.

1) ANN Classification:

The emergence of the artificial neural networks was influenced by the biological neural networks. It comprises a large network of interconnected neurons which exchange signals between each other. These

links have been given weight based on prior performance. As a result, it is an adaptable network that can learn [14].

Artificial neural networks are frequently employed to simulate complex patterns, make predictions, and solve classification issues. The general structure of an artificial neural network is shown in Fig. 3. There are many different optimization algorithms used during ANN training. Regarding demands, speed, and precision, they all perform differently and exhibit different characteristics. In order to select the right algorithm in line with the correct solution to the problem, we must be very precise. Gradient Descent (GD), Batch Back Propagation (BBP), Conjugate Gradient Descent (CGD), and Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) training algorithms are the primary optimization algorithms used in the training phase of multilayer networks. In our study, the nonlinear optimization algorithm LM algorithm was preferred for the classification process. The Newton's method in back propagation and the characteristics of gradient descent are combined in the LM algorithm, which was created by Kenneth Levenberg and Donald Marquardt [15]. It has been specifically created to operate with loss functions that have the structure of a sum of squared errors. It functions using the Jacobian matrix and the gradient vector.

$$f = \sum_{i=1}^m e_i^2 \quad (8)$$

The data set's instance count is indicated by the letter "m."

The LM algorithm's weight calculation equation is displayed in (9).

$$W = (J^T J + \mu U)^{-1} J^T e \quad (9)$$

Where J is the Jacobian matrix, which is made up of derivatives of errors at each weight, e is the network's error vector, and μ is a scalar, U unit matrix.

Figure 6: General Structure of Artificial Neural Network

2) K-NN Classification:

One of the most popular and straightforward classification algorithms for supervised machine learning is K-Nearest Neighbors, or KNN. It's a technique for classifying data that works by examining the data points nearby to determine what group a data point belongs in. A case is assigned to the class that is most popular among its K nearest neighbours as determined by a distance function based on the majority vote of its neighbours. The formal k-NN classifier algorithm is, in brief, as follows:

$$\text{arg min}(d_e(t, o, k)) \rightarrow \text{Identify P} \quad (10)$$

Where k is the number of closest neighbours to be taken into consideration, t is the training data, o is the object to be classified, P is the assigned class of the new object, and d_e is the Euclidean distance given by:

$$d_e(t, o, k) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^L (t_{i,k} - o_{i,k})^2} \quad (11)$$

Where L is the length of each of data vector.

We should pick the best K value and the best distance calculation technique in order to get the best results. For most datasets in the past, the ideal value of k has been between 3 and 10. There are various methods for calculating distance, but depending on the issue at hand, one method may be better. The Euclidean Distance, however, is the preferred option.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we compared artificial neural networks (ANN), K nearest neighbours, and machine learning classifiers (KNN). They helped us distinguish between PD patients and healthy people. The best score was produced by the ANN algorithm. Depending on the data set and the number of acoustic features used, the experiment results showed 96.7% classification accuracy for ANN. One of the programmes that is frequently used for this purpose is MATLAB. Many classification techniques are used today in the field of medical imaging in order to achieve the highest accuracy.

In order to improve the performance of classifiers and achieve the highest possible accuracy rating, this work can be expanded to include additional machine learning algorithms and a variety of datasets. From this angle, we plan to develop hybrid machine learning classifiers that combine ANN and KNN with other classifiers.

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